

The Effectiveness of the Vocational Training Programs for Women Prisoners at the 2nd Correctional Center in Cambodia

Chanthuch, TRY¹, Sokphat, KEO², Veasna, SOU³

^{1,2}Asia Euro University

³Royal University of Phnom Penh

Abstract- In the last decade, the situation in Cambodia has changed and developed significantly. In 1980, Cambodia had a population of about 6 million, but by 2019, Cambodia had a population of nearly 16 million, of which 18.5% were literate. Rapid growth has had social consequences, such as poverty, high school dropout, and unemployment. These adverse effects cause society to experience instability, insecurity, and disorder, such as fraud, robbery, murder, gambling, kidnapping, alcohol, and regular domestic violence, including drug trafficking and abuse. Among these crimes, drug trafficking and use are growing concerns in Cambodian society today. Drug consumption is not only increasing in the city, but it is also spreading to all parts of the countryside. Most importantly, drug cases have been seriously endangering the future of Cambodian youth. The study surveyed 124 female inmates at Correctional Center II to address research objectives and critical issues: (1) What are the programs for education, vocational training, and rehabilitation for detainees? (2) What is the attitude of female prisoners, and how are they satisfied with the vocational training programs? and (3) What are the challenges and solutions to improve this vocational education and training? This research used SPSS 25 Software to analyze the quantitative data on 124 female inmates. The results showed that the Second Correctional Center's management complies with legal standards and has a clear plan. In directing the daily work of prisoners, prison officials are not coerced, nor do they help solve complex problems for prisoners. Effective in safe, secure, and humane management, with a proper and hygienic environment and suitable management mechanisms to prevent torture and inhuman or degrading treatment of prisoners. Authorization and visitation services by detainees and careful medical examination and treatment. Indeed, the results of the effective prison management and the excellent attitude of the participants in this correctional center align with the prison management strategy under the 2011 Law on Prisons and human rights principles. As for the attitude of women prisoners towards vocational training, it is clear that vocational training is necessary for good opportunities to develop their future work and is beneficial. After participating in vocational training, the trainees had a positive attitude, felt less stressed during detention, and learned how to communicate with friends. Overall, through the actual work, we can see that there are still some challenges, such as the change of detainees, which gradually increases yearly, leading to detainees' detention and congestion. Indeed, detainees' attitudes are challenging to educate, modify, and rehabilitate because detainees are still at fault and have low attitudes, which is very complicated and a priority to be solved.

Keywords: Vocational Training Program, Women's Prisoner Satisfaction, Attitude and Adaptation, Internal Services, Leadership Practice, Leadership's Attitude, Vocational Program.

INTRODUCTION

The reintegration of ex-offenders into the community has emerged as a critical concern of the criminal justice system as prison populations have increased globally. High recidivism rates indicate that prisons have not adequately prepared many prisoners for life after prison (Ganapathy, 2018). Various critical models have been offered to explain prison maladjustment, broadly encompassing personal attributes and experiences of inmates interacting with institutional features. The importation model emphasizes prison misconduct derived from an inmate's personality style, traits, and values brought into prison as an expression of disruptive attitudes, aggressive behavior, and aberrant subcultural values in prison officers (Sorensen and Reidy, 2018). Therefore, educational and vocational training is essential for the reformation and rehabilitation of criminal offenders because education holds the capacity to change the lives of these offenders as they would become better citizens while contributing more to society upon release. Educated inmates can also secure jobs upon release leading to a drop in recidivism (Ajah, 2018). Vocational and training programs designed to deal with many inmates' educational and job-skill deficiencies might increase prisoners' chances of successful adjustment to society upon release from prison (Paulus and Dzindolet, 1992). Critically concerned, vocational and training programs allowed prisoners to enhance their internal and external resources and recognize environmental risk and protective factors that could influence their successful reintegration into society (Cesana et al., 2018). Training and vocational education can improve prison environments and transition to local communities by equipping incarcerated persons with building vocational skills, especially for women prisoners (Payne and Bryant, 2018).

More specifically, the formerly incarcerated individuals' benefits from correctional education are skills and tools that can carry over to their pursuit of higher education upon release. Research finds that correctional education positively impacts several post-release outcomes of incarcerated individuals, including recidivism rates (Donaldson and Viera, 2021, Hall, 2015), familial bonds, critical thinking skills, personal development (Baranger et al., 2018), and self-esteem (Parker, 1990). Previous studies have focused on correctional education and vocational training program impact on recidivism rates, defined as re-arrest, re-conviction, and re-

incarceration (Gaes, 2008, Hall, 2015). Findings from existing studies reveal that incarcerated individuals who participated in correctional education programming had lower rates of recidivism compared to those that did not (Kim and Clark, 2013, Nally et al., 2012). Indeed, another study found that correctional education not only lowers rates of recidivism but it also increases participation in educational opportunities (Gehring, 1997).

Prisoners to a future-looking optimistic perspective about how difficult it will be to return to the community (Cid et al., 2020). Transitioning from prison back into the community can be difficult for many individuals (Kjellstrand et al., 2022). Not only do re-entering individuals face a variety of issues that led to their imprisonment in the first place (e.g., poverty, low education, substance abuse, mental health issues, detrimental social networks), but also many experiences a host of new challenges related to their incarceration including securing safe and affordable housing, finding a livable-wage job, managing supervision expectations along with other work and family responsibilities, and accessing necessary mental and physical health care (Phelps, 2017). The recent research has consistently shown that gaining employment after release helps to reduce recidivism, but also that prisoners who have been in prison face many barriers to finding secure employment in the communities (Caroline et al., 2021). Training programs for vocational skills will support women prisoners to return home and can integrate into communities to improve their incomes and stable job. This activity can be reduced their return intention to prison effectively (Pettus-Davis, 2021). Among 474 participants in prison who had completed the training program, only 8% returned to prison on a new felony charge following completion (Sered et al., 2021). Prisoners return to home and community after being released with the vocational skills and attitudes that allow them to stay out of prison and reduce criminal intention (Luminita et al., 2021). Thus, correctional and vocational training curriculum or program plays a significant role in reducing crime intention and return intention to prison, as well as improving their living condition while applying for job skills to support their families.

“Good prison practices are essential for the well-being of prisoners and the wider community” (Bartels and Gaffney, 2011). They assist one of the most disadvantaged and vulnerable social groups and benefit the wider community by providing adequate social support and services to a group of people who will ultimately return to the community. The purposes of incarceration include not only retribution, punishment, deterrence, and incapacitation but also rehabilitation. For a prison to achieve this community and social interaction, it is essential to have prison practice models that support reintegration, facilitate personal development and reduce recidivism rates (Rubin, 2001). In Cambodia, the General Department of Prisons reported in June 2022 that there are 37,570 detainees. However, among 11, 018 prisoners and 145 women prisoners and 674 women foreigners, as well as 175 prisoners who have underage. Most inmates were drugs, accounting for 51.37%, aggravated theft 10.20%, theft 10.02%, rape 6.13%, murder 5.81%, and other crimes 16.47%. Meanwhile, the General Department of Prisons has released 9 889 inmates from court, including 737 women, and 99 died of chronic illness (Savuth, 2022). The purpose of offering a vocational training program for women prisoners is to facilitate their integration into the community and reduce the commitment to committing a crime and returning to prison. Therefore, the current study aims to conduct three main research objectives:

1. to evaluate the women's prison behavior to engage in the vocational training program.
2. to explore the critical challenges of the vocational training program.
3. to examine the key impacts of women's prison satisfaction with the vocational training program through internal services, leadership practice, and attitude in the correctional center.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Theoretical Foundation

The strain theory and the structural functionalism theory serve as the framework for this study. Strain theory was proposed by Merton (1957) which referred to Durkheim's notion of anomie, a social condition in which people with weak ties with the community find it difficult to know what to do because social norms are unclear or have broken down (Ajah, 2018). General Strain Theory (GST), initially promulgated by Agnew Agnew (1992), has demonstrated broad relevance within the criminal justice system to integrate criminological theories. A specific formulation has been applied to understand the progression or cessation of criminal behavior and violence during periods of incarceration, emphasizing the strain that individuals face upon entering prison and how they react to such experiences (Morris et al., 2012). Prison incarceration produces several strains leading to negative emotional and behavioral reactions depending on an individual's ability to cope with prison adversity. Such burdens include loss of freedom, autonomy, and independence; application of restrictions/rules; absence of privacy; restricted privileges; safety concerns around victimization or threat of harm; and other factors related to the staff or institution. Some inmates faced with chronic or cumulative strain are overwhelmed and may cope through deviant behavior, such as committing disciplinary violations and perpetrating violence on others (Sorensen and Reidy, 2018).

Hypotheses Development

The relationship between Prisoners' Internal Services and Prisoner's Attitude Adaptation

Perceptions of internal services offered by prison officers are associated with attitudes toward the prisoners' adaptation to prison's environment (Shannon and Page, 2014). Borrowing the service quality concept indicates that internal service providers will positively enhance customers' attitudes to adapt to their service environment (Cronin Jr and Taylor, 1994). Thus, this study posits that internal services provided by prison officers will positively influence prisoners' perception toward their attitude toward adapting to a new environment living in prison. Thus, the following hypothesis is proposed:

Hypothesis 1: Prisoners' internal services has a positive influence on prisoner's attitude adaptation

The Relationship between Leadership's Attitude and Prisoner's Attitude Adaptation

Prison officers interact with the specific interface between prisons (Moran and Turner, 2021). Also important are the views of the people who work in prison. Recent research has started to place the staff-prisoner relationship at the heart of understanding what

constitutes a 'good prison' (Maguire and Raynor, 2017). Through their daily communication with prisoners, prison staff can either undermine or support prisoner attitudes towards and engagement with rehabilitation (Maguire and Raynor, 2017, Blagden et al., 2016). Positive attitudes and beliefs about change held by prison staff and prisoners are vital for fostering effective offender rehabilitation and promoting change in offending behavior (Blagden et al., 2016). More generally, positive relations between prisoners and prison staff signify a view of prisoners as capable of positive change, whereas negative attitudes do the opposite (Kjelsberg et al., 2007). At the same time, staff can become very attached to the routines with which they are familiar and reluctant to alter their practices, meaning novel rehabilitative practices may not be prioritized (Craig, 2004). A climate that fosters rehabilitation requires the establishment of prisoner–staff relationships founded on empathy, compassion, trust, and mutual respect (Bullock and Bunce, 2018, Rowe and Soppitt, 2014). Another researcher indicated that the quality of the relationship between prison staff and the effectiveness of prison staff influences prisoners' perception of legitimacy in a prison environment and officer leadership's attitude (Hacin and Meško, 2018). Hence, the following hypothesis is proposed:

Hypothesis 2: Leadership's attitude has a positive influence on prisoner's attitude adaptation

The Relationship between Leadership Action and Practice and Prisoner's Attitude Adaptation

Both attitude and personality shape the behavior of individual prisoners on prison staff attitudes and leadership activities and practices in the prison (Crewe, 2012). Another study found that prison leaders support prisoners, which plays an essential role in shaping prisoners' attitudes and behavior toward adapting to the new living environment in prison (Jirathitikarn, 2020). The practices and attitudes of prison leaders play a critical role in influencing prisoners' attitudes toward adapting to life in the new environments (Allal-Chérif et al., 2021). Social learning theory suggests that a critical mass of individual prisoners with similar attitudes and behaviors would influence the broader leadership action and practice by providing alternative rewards for behaviors and attitudes perceived as significant (Thomas and Zaitzow, 2006). Therefore, the following hypothesis is proposed:

Hypothesis 3: Leadership action and practice has a positive influence on prisoner's attitude adaptation

The Relationship between Leadership Action and Practice and Trainee's Satisfaction

Leader action and practice in prison increase the need for women trainees' satisfaction with vocational training (Schuleigh et al., 2021). From a general perspective of leadership, leadership actions and practices in secondary school can foster teacher training satisfaction with teacher professionalism (Tyaningsih et al., 2021). Authentic leadership theory identifies the relevance of contextual factors, such as training and working setting, upon employees' perceptions and expectations of their leaders' practices (McPherson et al., 2022). Leadership practices could enhance satisfaction for the trainee to join the vocational training program in prison. Thus, the hypothesis is proposed:

Hypothesis 4: Leadership action and practice has a positive influence on trainee's satisfaction

The Relationship between Leadership's Attitude and Trainee's Satisfaction

Leadership attitude and skills enhanced the ability to communicate with women prisoners' satisfaction with vocational training programs to achieve their life goals when they return to the communities (Alsalamah and Callinan, 2021). Leadership attitudes who manage to teach methods to ensure our trainees are acquiring the knowledge and skills in joining the vocational training program to preserve trainee's satisfaction (Clifton, 2022). Authentic leadership style influences staff's attitudes and behaviors to enhance job satisfaction (McPherson et al., 2022). From the leadership theory perspective, the increasing complexity of leadership attitudes will impact baseline attitudes toward the perceptions and utility of a training development curriculum for the vocational training program in the correctional center for women prisoners in Cambodia. Therefore, the hypothesis is proposed:

Hypothesis 5: Leadership's attitude has a positive influence on trainee's satisfaction

The Relationship between Prisoner's Attitude Adaptation and Trainee's Satisfaction

Prisoners' high attitude toward adapting to life in prison will make them satisfied with the vocational training program, especially for women prisoners (Ward and Marshall, 2007, LeBel, 2007). Prisoners' attitudes, knowledge, and confidence in prison officers in prison, which lead to satisfaction with the vocational training program, were reported to be high (Ryan et al., 2022). According to Ajzen (1991), the Theory of Plan Behavior (TPB) explains and predicts how the attitude and social environment affect the individual's behavior, which relates to the attitude toward attending the vocational training program in prison. From this theoretical perspective, prisoners who have a high attitude toward adapting to the training environment will be satisfied with the training program developed by prison officers or leaders. Therefore, the following hypothesis is proposed:

Hypothesis 6: Prisoner's attitude adaptation has a positive influence on trainee's satisfaction

As proposed in Figure 1, the conceptual framework was integrated with previous theoretical backgrounds and existing literature reviews. Six proposed research hypotheses were operationalized key variables to examine their relationship by surveying vocational and training program in correctional center II of national prison in Phnom-Penh City, Cambodia. Most of these relationships have not been investigated yet by previous research scholars. Thus, this study asserts that the relationship among research variables can be existed and be validated.

Figure 2-1. Conceptual Framework of Trainees' Satisfaction

METHODOLOGY

Study sites

Correctional Center II for women prisoners is located in Phnom-Penh city, Cambodia. The research designed a self-administered survey and structured questionnaire for interviewing them in August 2021 and June 2022.

Sampling procedures

According to Cooper and Schindler (2014), the purposive sampling technique among non-probability sampling techniques was suitable to be adopted to collect the information from women prisoners who detained in 2020-2022. Indeed, known-population was developed by Yamane (1967) to determine the sample sizes for this study. Due to small population sizes of 128, the suggested sample sizes, 128 all women should participate in the survey. A total of 128 women were asked to participate in answering the questionnaire survey. A total of 128 questionnaires were collected. However, four questionnaires had to be excluded as outliers. The outliers were deleted using the graphic method, with a residual scatter plot in the range of ± 3 standard deviation (Hair et al., 2019). Finally, a total of 124 valid questionnaires were determined to be usable (a response rate of 89.85 percent) for further analyses. As suggested by Saunders et al. (2009), given that the likely response rate for questionnaires has been found to range between 30 and 50 percent, this response rate was viewed as adequate.

Measurement scales

All questionnaire items of research constructs were adopted from the existing research scholars. For example, "Trainees' Satisfaction" consists of five items adapted Lim and Morris (2006). A-9 items of "Prisoners' Leadership Attitude", and also "prisoners' Attitude Adaptation" consists of five items, adapted from Zhao et al. (2020). Five items of "Internal Services" in prison and four items of "Leadership Action and Practice" were developed by the own researcher. To survey in the Cambodian context, original items were translated into Khmer following Brislin's (1980) translation-back-translation procedure to validate the meanings of measurement items. All items were measured on a five-point Likert scale (1 =strongly disagree; 5= strongly agree). The Cronbach's alpha reliability for this study is reported in Table 1.

RESULTS

This manuscript was conducted in three stages to test the proposed research hypotheses. Firstly, Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) with SPSS 25 was performed to identify the underlying research variables of "Trainee's Satisfaction", "Attitude Adaptation", "Internal Services", "Leaderships' Attitude", "Leadership Action and Practice." Secondly, Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) was performed to test how well the measured variables represented the constructs and ensure the goodness of fit for the measurement model. Finally, the relationships among "Trainee's Satisfaction", "Attitude Adaptation", "Internal Services", "Leaderships' Attitude", "Leadership Action and Practice." were empirically tested using the Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) technique with AMOS 23. The purpose of performing these three stages of data analysis is to double-check on reliability and validity of research variables and the meanings of questionnaire items.

Factor Analysis and Reliability Test

Several purification processes, including factor analysis, correlation analysis, and internal consistency analysis (Cronbach's Alpha: α), are tested in this study. Exploratory factor analysis uses the principal component method with VARIMAX rotation to employ factor analysis and reliability tests to verify the research variables' dimensionality and reliability, as proposed in Figure 1. Factor analysis is first to identify the dimensionality of each research item. Theoretically, this section indicates that the threshold of the factor loading score of each item. Item-to-total correlation and coefficient Alpha (α) are accessed to examine the internal consistency and reliability of the primary research construct. According to (Hair-Jr et al., 2019), the following main key criterion must meet the threshold values, such as:

- The Factor Loading (FL) of each research item should be greater than 0.60,
- Eigenvalue should be greater than 1,
- The Cumulative percentage should be higher than 0.60,
- Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) should be higher than 0.50,
- Item-total-correlation should be greater than 0.50, and
- coefficient Alpha (α) should be higher than 0.60 or 0.70.

The cutoff values of the rules of thumb, as recommended by Hair et al. (2019) also adopted to evaluate the factor analysis and reliability test results indicated in Table 2. However, the results show that some research items have been deleted because it has not met the threshold values. Indeed, some research items contained factor loading value lower than criterion 0.60, thus also deleted. Most importantly, the rest of the research items of the formal reliability test were adopted to double-confirm with Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) and test the research hypotheses with Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) by performing AMOS 23 software.

The Factor Analysis and Reliability Test results indicate that most of the research variables and sub-dimension have met the cutoff value of rules of thumb as recommended by Hair et al. (2019). However, few of them have low reliability regarding their item-total correlation lower than 0.50 and Alpha <0.60 (i.e., "TSS1" belong to Trainee's Satisfaction; PAT1 & PAT5 belong to Attitude Adaptation; SA3, SA4, & SA3 belong to Internal Services; EAT2 & EAT3 belong to Leaderships' Attitude; and LA1 & LA3 belong to Leadership Action and Practice). Thus, for all research items shown in Table 1, this study proceeds with the CFA and SEM data analysis.

Table 1-Factor Analysis and Reliability test

Code*	Factor Analysis				Reliability Test	
	Factor Loading	KMO	Eigenvalue	Cummulative %	Item-to-total correlation	Cronbach's Alpha
Trainee's Satisfaction						
TSS5	0.884	0.748	3.003	75.066	0.785	0.889
TSS4	0.869				0.755	
TSS2	0.860				0.749	
TSS3	0.853				0.737	
TSS1	Deleted: Factor Loading <0.60					
Attitude Adaptation						
PAT3	0.865	0.669	2.024	67.460	0.657	0.758
PAT2	0.826				0.587	
PAT4	0.771				0.518	
PAT1	Deleted: Factor Loading <0.60					
PAT5						
Internal Services						
SA2	0.877	0.50	1.537	76.864	0.537	0.700
SA1	0.877				0.537	
SA3	Deleted: Factor Loading <0.60					
SA4						
SA5						
Leaderships' Attitude						
EAT6	0.826	0.848	3.081	61.618	0.705	0.844
EAT7	0.801				0.671	
EAT9	0.784				0.649	
EAT5	0.778				0.635	
EAT1	0.733				0.583	
EAT2	Deleted: Factor Loading <0.60					
EAT3						
EAT4						
EAT8						
Leadership Action and Practice						
LA4	0.862	0.50	1.485	74.244	0.485	0.653
LA2	0.862				0.485	

LA1	Deleted: Factor Loading <0.60
LA3	

Note: * Full meaning of all questionnaire items as listed in Appendix

Correlation Matrix

A Pearson correlation coefficient was calculated for the relationship among research variables. The results indicate a positive correlation and significant linear relationship between the two variables.

Table 2-Correlation Matrix (n=124)

Variables	Mean	Std. Deviation	TS	ATP	INS	LAT	LEAT
TS	3.55	0.58	1.00	.473**	.255**	.202*	.193*
ATP	3.66	0.44		1.00	.309**	.286**	.210*
INS	3.45	0.44			1.00	.432**	.540**
LAT	3.45	0.50				1.00	.484**
LEAT	3.51	0.41					1.00

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Note

TS= Trainee's Satisfaction

ATP= Attitude Adaptation

INS=Internal Services

LAT= Leaderships' Attitude

LEAT= Leadership Action and Practice

Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) or Measurement Model

The construct validity is assessed using the guidelines of Anderson and Gerbing (1988). First, the exploratory factor analysis for all the items resulted in factor solutions, as expected theoretically. The Cronbach Alpha coefficients for each factor were greater than 0.60. Second, we used confirmatory factor analyses (CFA) to assess the convergent validity of the measures.

Confirmatory factor analysis consists of main two-part for this manuscript, firstly related to the "First Order-Factor Model" and secondly related to the "Second Order-Factor Model" (Koufteros et al., 2009). This study adopted the first-order factor model to examine the research construct individually, as shown in the results in Appendix, respectively. The threshold values of CFA and SEM as shown in Table 4 were adopted to evaluate the results of CFA and SEM (i.e., Table 5). The results of the First-order factor model indicated that all the threshold values are very satisfied (upon available to request). Then, the second-order factor model was also adopted to examine the fitness of the overall model. All loadings exceed 0.60, and each indicator t-value exceeds 1.96 (p < 0.05), thus satisfying the CFA criteria. As shown in Table 5 and Figure 2, the overall goodness-of-fit assessment showed that $\chi^2/df = 1.065$, NFI = 0.906, CFI = 0.993, RMSEA=0.023. The results indicated that the research model could be presented as a good model fit with acceptable convergent validity. Since all values were greater than the established cutoff criteria, this study proceeds with hypothesis testing using structural equation modeling (SEM). Indeed, the Threshold of CFA and SEM was adopted to evaluate the results of this study, as shown in Table 5.

Table 3. The Threshold of CFA and SEM

Model Fit Statistics	Rule of Thumbs
$\chi^2/D.F$	< 3
GFI	≥ 0.90
AGFI	≥ 0.90
NFI	≥ 0.90
CFI	≥ 0.90
RMSEA	< 0.08

Sources: Anderson and Gerbing (1988), Jöreskog et al. (2016), Hair et al. (2014), Jöreskog and Sörbom (1993); Kline (2015), and Hooper et al. (2008).

Note:

Chi-square= χ^2

D.F= Degree of Freedom

GFI= Goodness of Fit

AGFI=Adjusted Goodness of Fit

NFI=Normed Fit Index

CFI=Comparative Fit Index

RMSEA =Root Mean Square Error of Approximation

The Average Variance Extracted (AVE) and Composite Reliability coefficients (CR) were applied to relate the quality of a measure. To avoid misconceptions, it is needed to appropriately understand the equations of the AVE and CR, as well as their association to the definition of validity and reliability. In this manuscript, we explain, using simulated one-factor models, how the number of items and the homogeneity of factor loadings might influence the AVE and CR results.

$$AVE = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n \lambda_i^2}{n} \quad (1)$$

$$CR = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n \lambda_i^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n \lambda_i^2 + \sum_{i=1}^n \delta_i} \quad (2)$$

Where: λ (Lamda) represents the standardized factor loading and i is the number of items (1) and δ (Delta) represents error variance terms (2) while $\delta = 1 - \lambda_i^2$.

According Fornell and Larcker (1981) and Peterson and Kim (2013), AVE must exceed 0.50, and CR must be exceed 0.70, respectively. Hair-Jr et al. (2019) recommend that t-value must be greater than 1.96 and p-value<0.05. All other criterion shown in Table 4 also need to evaluation the results of CFA and SEM.

Table 4-The Results of Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA)

Indicators		Research Constructs	Standardized Loading>0.60	t-value >1.96	AVE >0.50	CR >0.60
TSS2	←	Trainee's Satisfaction	0.869***	A	0.708	0.910
TSS3	←		0.775***	10.009		
TSS4	←		0.892***	9.65		
TSS5	←		0.824***	10.601		
PAT2	←	Attitude Adaptation	0.703***	A	0.533	0.770
PAT3	←		0.845***	7.549		
PAT4	←		0.626***	6.202		
SA1	←	Internal Services	0.702***	A	0.546	0.710
SA2	←		0.774***	5.84		
LA2	←	Leaderships' Attitude	0.657***	A	0.487	0.650
LA4	←		0.736***	4.842		
EAT5	←	Leadership Action and Practice	0.725***	8.302	0.467	0.850
EAT7	←		0.742***	8.563		
EAT6	←		0.795***	A		
EAT9	←		0.701***	7.839		
EAT1	←		0.657***	7.375		
Goodness-of-Fit Index						
$\chi^2/D.F = 1.461$						
NFI = 0.906						
CFI = 0.993						
RMSEA = 0.023						

Note:

AVE= Average Variance Extracted; CR= Composite Reliability; A= Parameter is fixed at regression weight equal to 1, and significant level of p-value<0.05 and t-value>1.96. ***p<0.001

Model=Standardized estimates
 Group=Group number 1
 Chi-sqaure=91.550,
 df=86, Chi-square/df=1.065,
 GFI=\GFI, AGFI=\AGFI,
 NFI=.906, CFI=.993,
 RMSEA=.023, P=.321

Figure 2-Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA)

Structural Equation Modeling (SEM)

To test the hypotheses, this study applies Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) with likelihood estimation method. The research variables have remained after CFA as shown in Table 4 was adopted to proceed with SEM. The second-order factor model is adopted to test the overall research variables (Anderson and Gerbing, 1988). The results show that goodness-of-fit measurements were acceptable (i.e., $\chi^2/df = 1.060$, CFI=0.905, NFI =0.994, and RMSEA=0.022) (see Table 5 and Figure 3) indicate that the proposed model was satisfactory with goodness-of-fit assessment (Hair et al., 2019). The CFA, which used the same variables as illustrated in Table 4, was run before proceeding with the SEM to test the likelihood estimation method. The results of Table 5 and Figure 3 show that good-ness-of-fit measurements were acceptable (i.e., $\chi^2/df = 1.065$, NFI = 0.906, CFI = 0.993, and RMSEA=0.023.); this indicates that the proposed model is satisfactory with goodness-of-fit assessment. The SEM model reveals the relationship between

“Leaderships’ Attitude” and “Attitude Adaptation” does not have a significant impact, which is $\beta = -0.11$, $p = 0.43$ ($p > 0.05$), and t -value $= -0.79$ (t -value < 1.96). Thus, Hypothesis 1 is rejected; The relationship of “Leaderships’ Attitude” has a positive and significant impact on “Internal Services”, which is $\beta = 0.55^{**}$, $p = 0.000 < 0.05$, and t -value $= 4.375 > 1.96$, which is accepted Hypothesis 2; The relationship of “Leadership Action and Practice” has a positive and significant impact on “Attitude Adaptation”, which is $\beta = 0.32^{**}$, $p = 0.016 < 0.05$, and t -value $= 2.40 > 1.96$, which is accepted Hypothesis 3; The relationship of “Leadership Action and Practice” has a positive and significant impact on “Internal Services”, which is $\beta = 0.26^{**}$, $p = 0.022 < 0.05$, and t -value $= 2.296 > 1.96$, which is accepted Hypothesis 4; The relationship of “Internal Services” has a positive and significant impact on “Attitude Adaptation”, which is $\beta = 0.41^{**}$, $p = 0.011 < 0.05$, and t -value $= 2.557 > 1.96$, which is accepted Hypothesis 5. The relationship of “Attitude Adaptation” has a positive and significant impact on “Trainee’s Satisfaction”, which is $\beta = 0.58^{***}$, $p = 0.000 < 0.001$, and t -value $= 5.429 > 1.96$, which is accepted Hypothesis 6. The SEM model indicates that the relationship of “Attitude Adaptation” played a vital role in enhancing “Trainee’s Satisfaction.”, because this relationship has $\beta = 0.58$ (58%) with highest and strongest significant impacted. Indeed, the proposed research all proposed six research hypotheses (H2-H5) are well-confirmed and supported.

Table 5-The Results of Structural Equation Modeling (SEM)

Constructs	Indicators		Standardized	t-value	p-value
			Coefficient (β)		
Trainee's Satisfaction	→	TSS2	0.875	A	***
	→	TSS3	0.770	9.921	***
	→	TSS4	0.990	10.086	***
	→	TSS5	0.807	10.343	***
Attitude Adaptation	→	PAT2	0.703	A	***
	→	PAT3	0.831	7.499	***
	→	PAT4	0.619	6.252	***
Internal Services	→	SA1	0.689	A	***
	→	SA2	0.751	5.124	***
Leaderships' Attitude	→	LA2	0.705	A	***
	→	LA4	0.688	4.377	***
Leadership Action and Practice	→	EAT5	0.721	8.587	***
	→	EAT7	0.717	8.635	***
	→	EAT6	0.827	A	***
	→	EAT9	0.700	8.069	***
	→	EAT1	0.634	7.277	***
Path Relationships					
H1: Leaderships' Attitude → Attitude Adaptation			-0.11	-0.79	0.43
H2: Leaderships' Attitude → Internal Services			0.55	4.375	0.000
H3: Leadership Action and Practice → Attitude Adaptation			0.32	2.40	0.016
H4: Leadership Action and Practice → Internal Services			0.26	2.296	0.022
H5: Internal Services → Attitude Adaptation			0.41	2.557	0.011
H6: Attitude Adaptation → Trainee's Satisfaction			0.58	5.429	0.000
Goodness-of-Fit Index					
$\chi^2/D.F=1.449$					
NFI=0.905					
CFI=0.994					
RMSEA=0.022					

Note:

A=parameter regression weight was fixed at 1.000 and significant level of p-value<0.05 and t-value>1.96. ***p<0.001

Figure 3-Structural Equation Modeling (SEM)

Chi-square test

The *Chi-Square Test* is adapted to determine if there is a statistically significant relationship between two dichotomous or nominal variables (Morgan et al., 2019). It tells us whether the relationship is statistically significant but does not indicate the strength of the relationship, like a correlation, such as a phi, does. This study investigates whether women prisoners' age and vocational training program differ on whether they have more high or low intention to join curriculum training skills; a chi-square statistic was conducted. Table 6 shows the Pearson chi-square results and indicates that women prisoners 'age and training programs are significantly different in whether they have high intention to join curriculum training programs (i.e., $\chi^2= 46.857, df= 20, n = 122, p=0.001$).

Table 6-The results of Chi-square test: Age vs Training Program

Training Programs	Age							Total
	18-25 Years	26-30 Years	31-35 Years	36-40 Years	41-45 Years	Over 45 Years		
• <i>Beautician</i>	7	15	7	4	1	4	38	
• <i>Sewing</i>	4	12	4	3	4	2	29	
• <i>Chef</i>	0	1	1	6	4	4	16	
• <i>Producer/Weaver</i>	2	0	2	0	0	1	5	
• <i>Other</i>	3	4	4	4	5	14	34	
Total	16	32	18	17	14	25	122	

Note: Pearson Chi-Square = 46.85, df=20, and significant of p-value = 0.001

Table 7 shows the Pearson chi-square results and indicates that women prisoners 'age and after release intention are significantly different in whether they have high intention to join any training program or own job creation (i.e., $\chi^2= 28.008, df= 15, n = 122, p=0.022$).

Table 7-The results of Chi-square test: Age vs After Release Intention

After Release Intention	Age							Total
	18-25 Years	26-30 Years	31-35 Years	36-40 Years	41-45 Years	Over 45 Years		
<i>Joint Training Program</i>	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	
<i>Joint Training Skills</i>	1	0	0	1	2	0	4	
<i>Own Job Creation</i>	10	17	9	6	2	4	48	
<i>Other</i>	5	14	9	10	10	21	69	
Total	16	32	18	17	14	25	122	

Note: Pearson Chi-Square = 28.008, df=15, and significant of p-value = 0.022 <0.05

ANOVA test

ANOVA is used to analyze nominal data by comparing three or more groups (Morgan et al., 2019) to identify the significant differences among research variables of (i.e., training skills, after release intention, and age) of women prisoners in the second correctional center and training programs (i.e., beautician, sewing, chef, producer/weaver, other). The results of Table 8 indicate that women prisoners perceived that training programs did not have a significant difference (F = 0.629, df=4, p=0.643) from training skills provided by correctional center II. Interestingly, training programs have significant difference with age (F = 3.907, df=4, p=0.005), and after release intention (F = 8.025, df=4, p=0.000).

Table 8- The Results of ANOVA test

ANOVA: Training Programs						
Variables		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
<i>Training Skills</i>	Between Groups	0.460	4	0.115	0.629	0.643
	Within Groups	21.758	119	0.183		
	Total	22.218	123			
<i>After Release Intention</i>	Between Groups	5.222	4	1.306	3.907	0.005
	Within Groups	39.770	119	0.334		
	Total	44.992	123			
<i>Age</i>	Between Groups	79.287	4	19.822	8.025	0.000

Within Groups	289.008	117	2.470		
Total	368.295	121			

CONCLUSIONS

Educational and vocational training is essential to any prison system that seeks to reduce crime and recidivism rates. It would bring positive change to prison inmates. Findings from this study indicate that the Cambodian prison system has neither implemented therapeutic programming nor has the necessary equipment/facilities to deliver it to the inmate population. Since education has been linked to reduced recidivism, proper programming and the facilities needed for its delivery must be developed, built, and adequately funded within the prison system. Furthermore, the government, especially the ministry of interior, should seek to meet local and international standards recognized as necessary for the safe and orderly operation of correctional facilities and meet humanitarian standards. Finally, an additional study should be conducted on Cambodia's prisons to obtain a more comprehensive idea regarding those areas of operation that need improvement. As a result of vocational training, women prisoners have the knowledge and skills to work in a career with sufficient income to spend when they return to communities. Vocational training helps reduce mental stress and reduces congestion within the prison. The prison has plenty of room for prisoners to organize rehabilitation activities for other prisoners, such as women prisoners, older prisoners, disabled prisoners, etc. This study would like to recommend that the government should first promote basic vocational training for prisoners and modify the training programs and procedures to suit the condition of the job market demands. This study recommends that policymakers ensure that there is a dedicated specialized employment team and vocational training team within the custodial environment providing individualized support for both unsentenced and sentenced people, both while they are incarcerated and post-release. In summary, these research findings from existing studies reveal that correctional education and vocational training program positively reduce recidivism and underscores the importance of making correctional education accessible to incarcerated individuals.

REFERENCES:

- AGNEW, R. 1992. Foundation for a general strain theory of crime and delinquency. *Criminology*, 30, 47-88.
- AJAH, B. O. 2018. Educational training of inmates in Awka and Abakaliki Prisons, Nigeria. *International Journal of Criminal Justice Sciences*, 13, 299-305.
- AJZEN, I. 1991. The theory of planned behavior. *Organizational Behavior and Human Decision Processes*, 50, 179-211.
- ALLAL-CHÉRIF, O., GUIJARRO-GARCÍA, M., BALLESTER-MIQUEL, J. C. & CARRILERO-CASTILLO, A. 2021. Being an ethical leader during the apocalypse: Lessons from the walking dead to face the COVID-19 crisis. *Journal of Business Research*, 133, 354-364.
- ALSALAMAH, A. & CALLINAN, C. 2021. Adaptation of Kirkpatrick's four-level model of training criteria to evaluate training programmes for head teachers. *Education Sciences*, 11, 116.
- ANDERSON, J. C. & GERBING, D. W. 1988. Structural equation modeling in practice: A review and recommended two-step approach. *Psychological Bulletin*, 103, 411-423.
- BARANGER, J., ROUSSEAU, D., MASTRORILLI, M. E. & MATESANZ, J. 2018. Doing time wisely: The social and personal benefits of higher education in prison. *The Prison Journal*, 98, 490-513.
- BARTELS, L. & GAFFNEY, A. 2011. Good practice in women's prisons: A literature review *Technical and Background Paper No 41, Australian Institute of Criminology*
- BLAGDEN, N., WINDER, B. & HAMES, C. 2016. "They treat us like human beings"—Experiencing a therapeutic sex offenders prison: Impact on prisoners and staff and implications for treatment. *International journal of offender therapy and comparative criminology*, 60, 371-396.
- BRISLIN, R. W. 1980. Handbook of Crosscultural Psychology. In: TRIANDIS, H. C. & BERRY, J. W. (eds.) *Translation and content analysis of oral and written material*. Boston, MA: Allyn & Bacon.
- BULLOCK, K. & BUNCE, A. 2018. 'The prison don't talk to you about getting out of prison': On why prisons in England and Wales fail to rehabilitate prisoners. *Criminology & Criminal Justice*, 20, 111-127.
- CAROLINE, D., SOPHIE, Y., LORANA, B., ANTHONY, H. & HELEN, T. 2021. 'If I don't get a job in six months' time, I can see myself being back in there': Post-prison employment experiences of people in Canberra. *Australian Journal of Social Issues*, 57, 627-643.
- CESANA, M. L., GIORDANO, F., BOERCHI, D., RIVOLTA, M. & CASTELLI, C. 2018. Drawing to reconstruct: Pilot study on acknowledging prisoners' internal and external resources in a penitentiary institution. *World Futures*, 74, 392-411.
- CID, J., PEDROSA, A., IBÁÑEZ, A. & MARTÍ, J. 2020. Does the Experience of Imprisonment Affect Optimism About Reentry? *The Prison Journal*, 101, 80-101.
- CLIFTON, W. 2022. Imparting knowledge to a unique generation of budding clinical anatomists. *Clinical Anatomy*, 35, 698-700.
- COOPER, D. R. & SCHINDLER, P. S. 2014. *Business research methods*, New York, McGraw Hil.
- CRAIG, S. C. 2004. Rehabilitation versus control: An organizational theory of prison management. *The Prison Journal*, 84, 92S-114S.
- CREWE, B. 2012. *The prisoner society: Power, adaptation and social life in an English prison*, OUP Oxford.
- CRONIN JR, J. J. & TAYLOR, S. A. 1994. SERVPERF versus SERVQUAL: reconciling performance-based and perceptions-minus-expectations measurement of service quality. *Journal of Marketing*, 58, 125-131.

20. DONALDSON, V. M. & VIERA, C. 2021. College after Prison: A Review of the Literature on Barriers and Supports to Postsecondary Education for Formerly Incarcerated College Students. *John Jay College Institute for Justice and Opportunity*.
21. FORNELL, C. & LARCKER, D. F. 1981. Structural equation models with unobservable variables and measurement error: Algebra and statistics. *Journal of Marketing Research*, 18, 382-388.
22. GAES, G. G. 2008. The impact of prison education programs on post-release outcomes. *Reentry Roundtable on Education, John Jay College of Criminal Justice, New York, March*, 31.
23. GANAPATHY, N. 2018. Rehabilitation, reintegration and recidivism: a theoretical and methodological reflection. *Asia Pacific Journal of Social Work and Development*, 28, 154-167.
24. GEHRING, T. 1997. Post-secondary education for inmates: An historical inquiry. *Journal of Correctional Education*, 46-55.
25. HACIN, R. & MEŠKO, G. 2018. Prisoners' perception of legitimacy of the prison staff: A qualitative study in Slovene prisons. *International journal of offender therapy and comparative criminology*, 62, 4332-4350.
26. HAIR-JR, J. F., BLACK, W. C., BABIN, B. J. & ANDERSON, R. E. 2019. *Multivariate data analysis*, New Jersey, Cengage.
27. HAIR, J. F., BLACK, W. C., BABIN, B. J. & ANDERSON, R. E. 2014. *Multivariate data analysis: Pearson new international edition*, Pearson Education.
28. HALL, L. L. 2015. Correctional education and recidivism: Toward a tool for reduction. *Journal of Correctional Education (1974-)*, 66, 4-29.
29. HOOPER, D., COUGHLAN, J. & MULLEN, M. 2008. Equation modelling: Guidelines for determining model fit. *Electronic Journal of Business Research Methods*, 6, 53-60.
30. JIRATHITIKARN, S. 2020. Policy implementation: Case studies of private sector and public sector to develop prisoners. *Kasetsart Journal of Social Sciences*, 41, 564-569.
31. JÖRESKOG, K. G., OLSSON, U. H. & WALLENTIN, F. Y. 2016. *Multivariate analysis with LISREL*, Switzerland, Springer.
32. JÖRESKOG, K. G. & SÖRBOM, D. 1993. *LISREL 8: Structural equation modeling with the SIMPLIS command language*, New York, Scientific Software International.
33. KIM, R. H. & CLARK, D. 2013. The effect of prison-based college education programs on recidivism: Propensity score matching approach. *Journal of Criminal Justice*, 41, 196-204.
34. KJELLSTRAND, J., CLARK, M., CAFFERY, C., SMITH, J. & EDDY, J. M. 2022. Reentering the community after prison: Perspectives on the role and importance of social support. *American Journal of Criminal Justice*, 47, 176-201.
35. KJELSBERG, E., SKOGLUND, T. H. & RUSTAD, A.-B. 2007. Attitudes towards prisoners, as reported by prison inmates, prison employees and college students. *BMC public health*, 7, 1-9.
36. KLINE, R. B. 2015. *Principles and practice of structural equation modeling*, Guilford publications.
37. KOUFTEROS, X., BABBAR, S. & KAIGHOBADI, M. 2009. A paradigm for examining second-order factor models employing structural equation modeling. *International Journal of Production Economics*, 120, 633-652.
38. LEBEL, T. P. 2007. An examination of the impact of formerly incarcerated persons helping others. *Journal of Offender Rehabilitation*, 46, 1-24.
39. LIM, D. H. & MORRIS, M. L. 2006. Influence of trainee characteristics, instructional satisfaction, and organizational climate on perceived learning and training transfer. *Human Resource Development Quarterly*, 17, 85-115.
40. LUMINITA, S. M., FLORICICA, C. M. & MARIUS, C. 2021. Social reinsertion of former detainees: Between perception and attitude. *Technium Soc. Sci. J.*, 25, 352.
41. MAGUIRE, M. & RAYNOR, P. 2017. Offender management in and after prison: The end of 'end to end'? *Criminology & Criminal Justice*, 17, 138-157.
42. MCPHERSON, K., BARNARD, J. G., TENNEY, M., HOLLIMAN, B. D., MORRISON, K., KNEELAND, P., LIN, C.-T. & MOSS, M. 2022. Burnout and the role of authentic leadership in academic medicine. *BMC Health Services Research*, 22, 627.
43. MERTON, R. K. 1957. *Strain theory*, New York, HarperCollins College Publishers.
44. MORAN, D. & TURNER, J. 2021. Drill, discipline and decency? Exploring the significance of prior military experience for prison staff culture. *Theoretical Criminology*, 26, 396-415.
45. MORGAN, G. A., BARRETT, K. C., LEECH, N. L. & GLOECKNER, G. W. 2019. *IBM SPSS for Introductory Statistics: Use and Interpretation: Use and Interpretation*, Routledge.
46. MORRIS, R. G., CARRIAGA, M. L., DIAMOND, B., PIQUERO, N. L. & PIQUERO, A. R. 2012. Does prison strain lead to prison misbehavior? An application of general strain theory to inmate misconduct. *Journal of Criminal Justice*, 40, 194-201.
47. NALLY, J., LOCKWOOD, S., KNUTSON, K. & HO, T. 2012. An evaluation of the effect of correctional education programs on post-release recidivism and employment: An empirical study in Indiana. *Journal of Correctional Education (1974-)*, 63, 69-89.
48. PARKER, E. A. 1990. The social-psychological impact of a college education on the prison inmate. *Journal of Correctional Education*, 140-146.
49. PAULUS, P. B. & DZINDOLET, M. T. 1992. The effects of prison confinement. In: SUEDFLED, P. & TETLOCK, P. E. (eds.) *Psychology and social policy*. Taylor & Francis.

50. PAYNE, Y. A. & BRYANT, A. 2018. Street Participatory Action Research in Prison: A Methodology to Challenge Privilege and Power in Correctional Facilities. *The Prison Journal*, 98, 449-469.
51. PETERSON, R. A. & KIM, Y. 2013. On the relationship between coefficient alpha and composite reliability. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 98, 194-198.
52. PETTUS-DAVIS, C. 2021. Support4Families: A Proposed Intervention Model to Support Families of Individuals Returning Home From Incarceration. *Families in Society*, 102, 316-332.
53. PHELPS, M. S. 2017. Mass probation and inequality: Race, class, and gender disparities in supervision and revocation. *Handbook on punishment decisions*. Routledge.
54. ROWE, M. & SOPPITT, S. 2014. 'Who you gonna call?' The role of trust and relationships in desistance from crime. *Probation Journal*, 61, 397-412.
55. RUBIN, E. L. 2001. The inevitability of rehabilitation. *Law & Inequality*, 19, 343-377.
56. RYAN, C., BRENNAN, F., MCNEILL, S. & O'KEEFFE, R. 2022. Prison officer training and education: a scoping review of the published literature. *Journal of Criminal Justice Education*, 33, 110-138.
57. SAUNDERS, M., LEWIS, P. & THORNHILL, A. 2009. *Research methods for business students*, Pearson education.
58. SCHULEIGH, V. E., MALOUFF, J. M., SCHUTTE, N. S. & LOI, N. M. 2021. Effects of Meeting Leader Training on Meeting Attendees. *Journal of Leadership Education*, 20.
59. SERED, S., TAFTE, E. & RUSSELL, C. 2021. Ineffectiveness of prison-based therapy: The case for community-based alternatives. Susan Sered, PhD. <http://susan.sered.name/blog/debunking-the-myth-of-...>
60. SHANNON, S. K. & PAGE, J. 2014. Bureaucrats on the cell block: Prison officers' perceptions of work environment and attitudes toward prisoners. *Social Service Review*, 88, 630-657.
61. SORENSEN, J. R. & REIDY, T. J. 2018. Nothing to Lose? An Examination of Prison Misconduct Among Life-Without-Parole Inmates. *The Prison Journal*, 99, 46-65.
62. THOMAS, J. & ZAITZOW, B. H. 2006. Conning or conversion? The role of religion in prison coping. *The Prison Journal*, 86, 242-259.
63. TYANINGSIH, A. R., SURYADI, S. & RAHMAWATI, D. 2021. Self-efficacy, teacher leadership and teacher professionalism in secondary school. *Jurnal Iqra': Kajian Ilmu Pendidikan*, 6, 1-12.
64. WARD, T. & MARSHALL, B. 2007. Narrative identity and offender rehabilitation. *International Journal of Offender Therapy and Comparative Criminology*, 51, 279-297.
65. YAMANE, T. 1967. *Statistics: An introductory analysis*, New York., Harper and Row.
66. ZHAO, J., WANG, X. & ZHANG, H. 2020. The role of perceived legitimacy and its effect on prison adaptation: A longitudinal study on a Chinese Juvenile prison. *International Journal of Offender Therapy and Comparative Criminology*, 64, 100-123.

APPENDIX: Questionnaire Design

Trainee's Satisfaction ($\alpha = 0.889$)

- TSS1 This vocational training program provides the training content I need for my job.
- TSS2 This vocational training program is useful in fulfilling some of the current tasks I am doing.
- TSS3 I like the content of this vocational training program
- TSS4 I appreciate the teachers who teach this vocational training program.

Attitude Adaptation ($\alpha = 0.758$)

- PAT1 This second correctional center facility provides me with adequate educational and vocational programs as well as other recreational activities.
- PAT2 The educational and vocational programs offered here are very helpful and I am willing to participate.
- PAT3 After participating in these vocational training programs, I felt that I had a positive attitude toward my life while incarcerated.
- PAT4 After participating in these training programs, I learned how to reduce stress during incarceration.
- PAT5 After participating in these training programs, I learned how to communicate with friends during incarceration.

Internal Services ($\alpha = 0.700$)

- SA1 Accommodation in the area: Water consumption
- SA2 Provision of food
- SA3 Provision of daily necessities
- SA4 Authorization and provision of visiting services
- SA5 Medical examination and treatment services

Leaderships' Attitude ($\alpha = 0.844$)

- EAT1 Correctional officers in this center are polite

- EAT2 Correctional officers in this center provide justice to equal prisoners
- EAT3 Correctional officers in the center are effective in managing crime and protecting lives and property.
- EAT4 I am confident with the correctional officers in this center
- EAT5 Correctional officers in this center are respectable.
- EAT6 Correctional officers in this center have a good relationship with me
- EAT7 In general, correctional officers are willing to help us
- EAT8 I generally like working with correctional officers in this center.

Leadership Action and Practice ($\alpha = 0.653$)

- LA1 Planning with the participation of leading officials
- LA2 Leading daily work with coercion
- LA3 Solving your Difficulty
- LA4 Wages from productive work